

Synthesis of First Cyclooligosaccharides of L-Series, Cycloawaodorins[†]

MUGIO NISHIZAWA* and HIROSHI IMAGAWA

Faculty of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Tokushima Bunri University, Yamashiro-cho, Tokushima 770-8514, Japan

Manuscript received 1 September 1998

Well-known cyclooligosaccharides, α -, β -, and γ -cyclodextrins are prepared in a large scale by enzymatic methods¹, and employed for an important host molecule in industry to include drugs and flavors². Modifications of cyclodextrins are also important subject, and large numbers of investigation have been carried out³. Cyclooligosaccharides have also been focussed as the synthetic target molecule, and after Ogawa's first total synthesis of α -cyclodextrin⁴⁻⁶, variety of synthetic studies have been carried out⁷⁻¹⁵. However, available cyclooligosaccharides were only limited to D-series. We have developed a novel and economical thermal glycosylation procedure^{16,17}, which is particularly useful for partially mannosylation and rhamnosylation with virtually complete α -selectivity¹⁸. Thus we have connected two L-rhamnose units to give L-rhamnose 1,4-dimer. On further elongation of rhamnosyl chain to trimer, tetramer and pentamer, we arrived rhamnose 1,4-hexamer by the α -selective thermal glycosylation. Then the cyclization of the hexamer at both ends afforded the first cyclooligosaccharide

of L-series **1**¹⁹. We named ' α -cycloawaodorin'²⁰ to the first L-series cyclooligosaccharide in connection with the area where the compound has been prepared. Synthesis of β -cycloawaodorin (cyclo-L-rhamnoheptaose **2**)²¹, γ -cycloawaodorin (cyclo-L-rhamnooctaose **3**) and cyclo-L-rhamnopentaose (**4**)²² have also been achieved and characterized (Chart 1). Preliminary investigations of inclusion experiment of α -cycloawaodorin with methyl sorbate have been investigated and are mentioned briefly.

Chemical synthesis of cyclooligosaccharide

In 1985, Ogawa and coworkers reported the total synthesis of α -cyclodextrin⁴⁻⁶, that is the first synthesis of cyclooligosaccharide. They have prepared liner hexamer using maltose as the starting material and achieved cycloglycosylation by Mukaiyama's procedure using SnCl₂ and AgOTf²³. γ -Cyclodextrin has also been synthesized by the strategy⁵. Synthesis of cyclo-D-mannohexaose was also reported by Ogawa and coworkers by means of Schmidt's imidate method and PhSeOTf promoted

Chart 1

Fig 1

cycloglycosylation²⁴⁻²⁶. Therefore, all known cyclooligosaccharides were limited to the D-series sugars before our investigation²⁷.

Developments of the thermal glycosylation

In 1901, Konigs and Knorr reported the classical glycosylation method that condenses alcohol and glycosyl

bromide in the presence of silver or mercuric salts²⁸. Recently, large numbers of modern glycosylation procedures have been developed due to explosive biological interest toward glycosyl chain and glycopeptide area. During our synthetic study of intensely sweet glycosides, baymoside (5)²⁹⁻³¹ and oleanin (6)^{32,33}, we have also developed an original very simple glycosylation procedure, thermal

Scheme 1

Scheme 2. *Reagents and condition*: (a) allyl alcohol, CSA (0.1 eq), reflux, 9 h, (b) acetone dimethylacetal (5 eq), TSOH (0.01 eq), DMF/acetone, RT, 4 h, (c) Ac₂O, pyridine, RT, 3 steps 79%, (d) TFA/MeOH, 2 : 1, 30 min, 100%, (e) Bu₂SnO (1.7 eq), toluene, reflux 2 h, then benzyl bromide (5 eq), n-BuNF (1.2 eq), RT, 12 h, 85%, (f) NaH (5 eq), benzyl bromide (3 eq), DMF, 75 min, 80%, (g) (Ph₃P)₃RhCl (0.0005 eq), DABCO (0.2 eq), Ph₃P (0.2 eq), benzene/EtOH/H₂O, 7 : 3 : 1, reflux, 1 h, 99%, (h) SeO₂ (1.0 eq), H₂O₂, MeCN/phosphate buffer (pH 7), RT, 3 h, 100%, (i) SOCl₂, DMF (cat), CH₂Cl₂, RT, 97%.

Scheme 3. *Reagents and condition*: (a) (n-C₄H₉)₃SnSMe (1.7 eq), BF₃ (1.0 eq), CH₂Cl₂, (b) MeONa, MeOH, RT, (c) 8 (2–4 eq), TMU (3–6 eq), 70–100°, 24–160 h, (d) DMTST, CH₂Cl₂, (f) NH₃, Li.

glycosylation. Without using any metal salt, glycosides can be produced by simply heating a neat mixture of alcohol and glycosyl chloride in the presence of acid scavenger, tetramethylurea (TMU)^{16–18}. Drying operation is of prime importance, and we have dried the reaction mixture after closing the reaction system using apparatus I (Fig. 1). A solution of alcohol, glycosyl chloride and TMU in dichloromethane was heated to reflux azeotropically for 2–3 h through a column packed with molecular sieves, then the stopcock was closed to trap the solvent into the upper column and the residual neat mixture was heated to 70–120°. Although the glucosylation, xylosylation and

galactosylation did not afford any stereoselectivity, mannosylation and particularly rhamnosylation furnished with high α -selectivity¹⁸.

Synthesis of L-series cyclooligosaccharide

Synthesis of α -cycloawaodorin (cyclo-L-rhamnohexaose) :

A virtually complete α -selective rhamnosylation in hand, we designed the synthesis of the first L-series cyclooligosaccharide by connecting L-rhamnose units²⁰. We found thiomethyl group at the C-1 position of rhamnosyl residue suffer against thermal glycosylation condition. Thus it played not only as the protecting group during the chain elongation

Fig. 2. 400 MHz ^1H nmr of hexamer alcohol **24** in CDCl_3 .

step but also as the activating group on cycloglycosylation as seen in the retrosynthetic scheme (Scheme 1). Therefore, we choose stepwise elongation strategy to afford the linear rhamnosyl chain, which will be able to extend to the solid phase synthesis.

L-Rhamnose (**7**) was successively protected by allylation (1-OH), ketalization (2,3-diol) and acetylation (4-OH), to give **11** in 79% overall yield. After acidic cleavage of ketal moiety to the diol **12**, 3-hydroxyl group was selectively benzylated by using dibutyltin oxide³⁴ and benzyl bromide

affording the monobenzyl ether **13**. The remaining hydroxyl group was again benzylated by benzyl bromide and NaH in DMF to give allyl 2,3-O-benzyl-4-O-acetyl- α -L-rhamno-pyranoside (**14**). The allyl group was removed in two steps sequence by rhodium catalyzed isomerization of the double bond into 1,2-position followed by an oxidative hydrolysis using H_2O_2 - SeO_2 in acetonitrile and phosphate buffer to give the hemiacetal **16** in quantitative yield. Treatment of **16** with SOCl_2 afforded the α -rhamnosyl chloride **8** selectively (Scheme 2). The monomeric chloride **8** was obtained

Fig. 3. 600 MHz ^1H nmr of **1b** in CDCl_3 .

Fig. 4. 600 MHz ^1H nmr of α -cycloawaodorin (1) in D_2O .

by 9 steps in total 57% yield.

The rhamnopyranosyl chloride **8** was treated with $(n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9)_3\text{SnSMe}^{35,36}$ (1.7 equiv) in the presence of $\text{BF}_3\text{-Et}_2\text{O}$ (1 equiv) in CH_2Cl_2 to give easily separable α - and β -thiomethyl rhamnosides **17a** and **17b** in 91% yield in 2 : 3 ratio respectively. Although both the isomers should be useful for the synthesis, we employed purified α -isomer **17a** for the following steps. After methanolysis of the acetyl group of **17a**, the resulting 4-hydroxy compound **9** was subjected

to the thermal rhamnosylation. After drying operation, a neat mixture of **9**, rhamnosyl chloride **8** (2.7 equiv) and TMU (3 equiv) was heated at 80° for 87 h to give the dimer **18** (70%). The stereochemistry at the newly formed glycosidic bond was completely controlled to the α . The acetyl group of **18** was hydrolyzed to the dimer alcohol **19**, and the mixture of **19** and **8** was heated at 70° for 134 h to give the trimer in 97% yield. The tetramer **21** was obtained by heating **8** at 80° for 150 h in 81% yield after hydrolysis. By heating a

Scheme 4

Fig. 5. 600 MHz ^1H nmr of β -cycloawaadorin (2) in D_2O .

mixture of **21** and **8** at 80° for 153 h, the pentamer **22** was obtained in 79% yield. The pentamer alcohol was treated with **8** at 80° for 168 h affording the hexamer **23** in 88% yield, and hydrolysis furnished the hexamer alcohol **24**. Stereoselectivity of each rhamnosylation reaction was extremely high, and the β -isomers were not detected at all.

Although the Ogawa's cycloglycosylation procedure using phenylselenenyl triflate²⁴ afforded poor result, large

excess (60 equiv) of dimethylmethylthiosulfonium triflate (DMTST)^{37,38} resulted clean cyclization. The cyclic hexamer **1b** was obtained in 90% yield as colorless needles (m.p. 171 - 173°) by the reaction dichloromethane for a day (Scheme 3). Although the ^1H nmr of the linear hexamer **24** was very complicated with six sets of doublet methyl groups and anomeric protons (Fig. 2), cyclic hexamer **1b** exhibited very simple monomer-like ^1H nmr owing to the C6 symme-

Fig. 6. 600 MHz ^1H nmr of iso- β -cycloawaadorin (26) in D_2O .

Scheme 5

try (Fig. 3). The Birch reduction of 1b simultaneously cleaved twelve benzyl groups to give the first cyclooligosaccharide of L-series. The product 1 also exhibited sharp monomer-like ^1H (Fig. 4) and ^{13}C nmr spectra in D_2O . Molecular formula $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{60}\text{O}_{24}$ was confirmed by high resolution FAB mass spectrum of m/z 899.3228 and 915.3068, which correspond to $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{60}\text{O}_{24}\text{Na}$ (899.3372) and $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{60}\text{O}_{24}\text{K}$ (915.3111) respectively. We decided to call this first cyclooligosaccharide of the L-series to be α -cycloawaadorin in connection with old areal name of Tokushima (Awa). α -Cycloawaadorin (1) is moderately soluble in water and methanol but hardly soluble in most of organic solvents such as chloroform, acetone, acetonitrile and pyridine.

Synthesis of β -cycloawaadorin (cyclo-L-rhamnoheptaose)²¹:

To prepare the L-rhamnose liner heptamer, we need to introduce one more rhamnose unit to 24. After drying operation (Fig. 1), a neat mixture of the liner hexamer 24, rhamnosyl chloride 8 (3 equiv) and TMU (3 equiv) was heated at 80° for 96 h and subsequent hydrolysis afforded the heptamer 25 in 85% yield with complete α -selectivity (Scheme 4). DMTST induced cycloglycosylation of 25 was also carried out using motor syringe drive during a period of 4 days, however, the obtained cyclic L-rhamnose heptamer was a mixture of the stereoisomers. The mixture was subjected to Li/NH_3 reduction to cleave fourteen benzyl groups simultaneously. At this stage we found the deprotected ste-

Fig. 7. 600 MHz ^1H nmr of γ -cycloawaadorin (3) in D_2O .

Scheme 6. Reagents and condition: (a) CCl_3CN , DBU, CH_2Cl_2 , (b) TMSOTf, **27**, (c) separation, (d) NaOMe, MeOH, (e) HPLC separation, (f) DMTST, (g) $\text{Pd}(\text{OH})_2$, H_2 .

reoisomers showing totally different R_f values on tlc and these were easily separated by ODS column chromatography. Both the products **2** (R_f 0.2 by MeOH- H_2O , 2 : 1) and **26** (R_f 0.8) showed same molecular formula $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{70}\text{O}_{28}$ based on the high resolution FAB mass spectrum that corre-

ponds to rhamnose cyclic heptamers.

^1H (Fig. 5) and ^{13}C nmr of **2** in D_2O indicate that this compound has a symmetrical cyclic L-rhamnose heptamer, namely, β -cycloawaodorin. On the other hand, nmr spectrum of **25** was very complicated (Fig. 6). According to

Fig. 8. 600 MHz ^1H nmr of cyclo-L-rhamnopentaose (**4**) in D_2O .

HSQC and HMBC experiments, most of the proton and carbon signals were assigned. Particularly, the consecutive three rhamnose units G, A, and B were assigned completely. ROE relationships of H^{A4} with H^{B1} , H^{B4} with H^{C1} , H^{C4} with H^{D1} , H^{D4} with H^{E1} , H^{E4} with H^{F1} , and H^{F4} with H^{G1} were observed on ROESY experiments. Although no rela-

tionship was detected between H^{G4} and H^{A1} , a cross peak between H^{G3} and H^{A1} suggested the cyclic structure of **26**. Furthermore, the cyclic structure of **26** was also confirmed by detecting cross peaks between C^{A4} and H^{B1} , C^{B4} and H^{C1} , C^{C4} and H^{D1} , C^{D4} and H^{E1} , C^{E4} and H^{F1} , C^{F4} and H^{G1} , and C^{G4} and H^{A1} on HMBC. ROE cross peaks of

Fig 9 600 MHz ^1H nmr of methyl sorbate (**32**) and α -cycloawaadorin (**1**) inclusion complex in D_2O

Fig. 10. 600 MHz NOESY spectrum of methyl sorbate and α -cycloawaadorin inclusion complex.

H^{A1} with H^{A3} and H^{A5} indicated β -glycosidic linkage between rhamnoses G and A. Therefore, **26** is also cyclic L-rhamnose heptamer and stereoisomeric with **2** at one of the anomeric centers. Thus we named **26** as iso- β -cycloawaadorin.

Synthesis of γ -cycloawaadorin (cyclo-L-rhamnooctaose) :

By further thermal rhamnosylation of the heptamer **25** with rhamnosyl chloride **8** (3 equiv) and TMU (3 equiv) at 80° for 96 h, and following hydrolysis, the L-rhamnose octamer **28** was obtained in 90% yield (Scheme 5). Again, the stereoselectivity was virtually complete. Cyclization of the octamer alcohol **28** was carried out under the same conditions described before, and the stereoselective cyclization took place to give the symmetrical octamer **3b** in 31% yield. After deprotection by the Birch reduction, cyclic L-rhamnose octamer, γ -cycloawaadorin (**3**) was obtained. ^1H nmr in D_2O showed that this compound takes simple monomeric pattern (Fig. 7). Molecular formula $\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{80}\text{O}_{32}$ was confirmed by high resolution FAB mass spectrum : m/z 1207.4250 (found), 1207.4270 (calcd. for $\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{80}\text{O}_{32}\text{K}$).

Synthesis of cyclo-L-rhamnopentaose²² :

Since the degradation of starch by amylase does not produce pentameric oligosaccharide, cyclic pentaose is unknown until recently. The first cyclic pentaose, cyclo-D-mannopentaose, was synthesized in 1993 by Ogawa's group³⁹, and cyclo-D-glucopentaose by Nakagawa's group⁴⁰ in 1994. When we designed the synthesis of cyclo-L-rhamnopentaose

(**4**), we decided to employ Schmidt's imidate glycosylation procedure⁴¹ to elongate rhamnose chain and compare the efficiency with our thermal rhamnosylation. Thus the imidate **27** was prepared by the reaction of rhamnose derivative **16** with trichloroacetonitrile in the presence of DBU (Scheme 6). Only 3 min was enough to couple the imidate **27** and the alcohol **9** in the presence of TMSOTf (0.1 equiv) in dichloromethane. However, the stereoselectivity was not very high and α -rhamnosides were obtained in 73% yield along with 5% of β -isomer after silica gel column chromatography. Glycosylation of hydrolyzed **18** with **27** under analogous conditions afforded a trimer **29** in 71% yield together with 6% of β -isomer. The stereoisomers were easily separated as before. Hydrolysis and further rhamnosylation afforded a hardly separable mixture of the α -tetramer and its β -isomer. However, the α -tetramer **21** (70%) and the β -isomer (8%) were separated after hydrolysis by column chromatography. The final (4+1)condensation afforded a mixture of the pentamers **30**, however, the separations of stereo-isomers of the acetate as well as the hydroxy derivatives were no more possible by open column chromatography. Thus the hydrolyzed mixture was subjected to HPLC (YMC-gel-ODSA-150, MeOH/ H_2O , 3 : 1) to give the pentamer alcohol **31** in 87% yield along with 9% of β -isomer. Thus the elongation of the rhamnose chain was efficiently achieved by Schmidt's imidate method within a few minutes unless the separations of stereoisomers are not significant matter, since undesired β -isomer was always formed in 5–9% yield.

Fig. 11. NOESY correlations of methyl sorbate and α -cycloawaodorin.

The stereoselectivity of our thermal rhamnosylation is virtually complete to give only α -rhamnoside though it claims very long reaction period (50–150 h) at relatively lower temperature (70–80°) to acquire satisfactory yield. Cycloglycosylation of the pentamer alcohol was another difficult job, and the treatment with DMTST (30 equiv) under dilution conditions at room temperature afforded cyclic pentamer **4b** in only 20% yield. Hydrogenolysis of **4b** catalyzed by $\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$ afforded cyclo-L-rhamnopentaose (**4**). ^1H and ^{13}C nmr of **4** gave an essentially rhamnose monomer pattern (Fig. 8). Each signal appeared rather sharp than hexamer at room temperature reflecting the conformational rigidity. Finally, the size of this molecule was confirmed by determining FAB mass spectrum. A peak observed at m/z 753 was attributed to $(\text{M}+\text{Na})^+$ ion, and $(\text{M}+\text{K})^+$ ion was observed at m/z 769 supporting the structure of rhamnose pentamer. No trace signal was detected around m/z 1460 that corresponds to rhamnose decamer.

The difficulty of the cyclization of pentamer should be depended upon the increase of strain that is expected from the CPK model. On the other hand, hexamer can take ideal conformation to cyclize and as high as 90% yield was achieved in cyclization. Low yield and no stereoselectivity in the cyclization of heptamer should be depended on entropy factor at least in part. Increased entropy factor of octamer should reduce the chance to cyclize leading low yield.

Inclusion study of α -cycloawaodorin

Most important property of cyclooligosaccharide was inclusion ability as host molecule, and we have been very much interested in the inclusion chemistry of cycloawaodorins. Although the detection of inclusion phenomena has been carried out by a variety of procedure, we employed nmr analysis to get preliminary information to detect the inclusion with α -cycloawaodorin. Since the standard guest compound, *p*-nitrophenol was not incorporated in

α -cycloawaodorin (**1**) probably due to the smaller size of cavity, we employed methyl sorbate (**32**). According to the addition of methyl sorbate, chemical shifts of H-1, H-3, H-4 and H-5 of α -cycloawaodorin (**1**) moved higher field gradually, though only H-2 moved lower field (Fig. 9). NOESY spectrum of the 1:1 mixture of methyl sorbate and α -cycloawaodorin in D_2O indicated those NOE relationships between H-3 with H-3' and H-4', H-5 with H-3' and H-4', H-3 with H-6', H-5 with H-6', H-6 with methoxy group (Fig. 10). Thus we detected that α -cycloawaodorin included methyl sorbate definitely, where H-3 and H-5 of α -cycloawaodorin are located inside of the cavity. NOE between H-3 and vinyl methyl (H-6') as well as rhamnosyl methyl (H-6) and methyl group of sorbate clearly elucidated the direction of inclusion as seen in Fig. 11.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. H. Yamada and Dr. T. Sugihara for helpful discussion. They thank M.S. Y. Kan, Ms. K. Kubo, M.S. E. Morikuni and M.S. I. Hyodo for their contribution to this study.

References

1. (a) D. FRENCH, *Adv. Carbohydr. Chem.*, 1957, **12**, 189; (b) W. SAENGER, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1980, **19**, 344.
2. K. UEKAMA and F. HIRAYAMA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1978, **26**, 1195.
3. M. L. BENDER and M. KOMIYAMA, "Cyclodextrin Chemistry, Reactivity and Structure", Concepts in Organic Chemistry 6, Springer-Verlag, 1978.
4. T. OGAWA and Y. TAKAHASHI, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1985, **138**, C5.
5. Y. TAKAHASHI and T. OGAWA, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1987, **164**, 277.
6. Y. TAKAHASHI and T. OGAWA, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1987, **169**, 127.
7. P. M. COLLINS and M. H. ALI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, **31**, 4517.
8. S. COTTAZ and H. DRIGUEZ, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1989, 1088.
9. P. R. ASHTON, P. ELLWOOD, I. STATON and J. F. STODDART, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1991, **30**, 80.
10. N. SAKAIRI, L. X. WANG and H. KUZUHARA, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1991, 289.
11. N. SAKAIRI and H. KUZUHARA, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1992, 510.
12. N. SAKAIRI and H. KUZUHARA, *Chem. Lett.*, 1993, 1093.
13. N. SAKAIRI and H. KUZUHARA, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1993, 1874.
14. K. FUJITA, K. OHTA, Y. IKEGAMI, H. SHIMADA, T. TAHARA, Y. NOGAMI, T. KOGA, K. SAITO and T. NAKAJIMA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1994, **51**, 9577.
15. G. GATTUSO, S. A. NEPOGODIEV and J. F. STODDART, *Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **98**, 1919.
16. M. NISHIZAWA, Y. KAN and H. YAMADA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1988, **29**, 4597.

17. M. NISHIZAWA, Y. KAN and H. YAMADA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1989, **37**, 565.
18. M. NISHIZAWA, Y. KAN, W. SHIMOMOTO and H. YAMADA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, **31**, 2431.
19. M. NISHIZAWA, H. IMAGAWA, Y. KAN and H. YAMADA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1991, **32**, 5551.
20. M. NISHIZAWA, H. IMAGAWA, K. KUBO, Y. KAN and H. YAMADA, *Synlett*, 1992, 447.
21. M. NISHIZAWA, H. IMAGAWA, I. HYODO, Y. KAN and H. YAMADA, *Heterocycles*, 1997, **44**, 71.
22. M. NISHIZAWA, H. IMAGAWA, E. MORIKUNI, S. HATAKEYAMA and H. YAMADA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1994, **42**, 1365.
23. T. MUKAIYAMA, Y. MURAI and S. SHODA, *Chem. Lett.*, 1981, 431.
24. (a) M. MORI, Y. ITO and T. OGAWA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1989, **30**, 1273; (b) M. MORI, Y. ITO and T. OGAWA, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1989, **192**, 131.
25. M. MORI, Y. ITO and T. OGAWA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, **31**, 3029.
26. M. MORI, Y. ITO, J. UZAWA and T. OGAWA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1990, **31**, 3191.
27. Recently, synthesis of cyclooligosaccharide containing L-sugar was reported : (a) P. R. ASHTON, S. J. CANTRILL, G. GATTUSO, S. MENZER, S. A. NEPOGODIEV, A. N. SHIPWAY, J. F. STODDART and D. J. WILLIAMS, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 1997, **3**, 1299; (b) P. R. ASHTON, C. L. BROWN, S. MENZER, S. A. NEPOGODIEV, J. F. STODDART and D. J. WILLIAMS, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 1996, **2**, 580.
28. W. KOENIGS and E. KNORR, *Chem. Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 957.
29. M. NISHIZAWA, H. YAMADA and Y. HAYASHI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1986, **27**, 3255; *J. Org. Chem.*, 1987, **52**, 4878.
30. H. YAMADA and M. NISHIZAWA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1987, **28**, 4315.
31. H. YAMADA and M. NISHIZAWA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1992, **48**, 3021.
32. H. YAMADA, M. NISHIZAWA and C. KATAYAMA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1992, **33**, 4009.
33. M. NISHIZAWA and H. YAMADA, *Synlett*, 1993, 54.
34. N. NAGASHIMA and M. OHNO, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1991, **39**, 1972.
35. E. W. ABE and D. A. ARMITAGE, *Adv. Organomet. Chem.*, 1967, **5**, 2.
36. T. OGAWA and M. MATSUI, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1977, **54**, C17.
37. M. RAVENSCROFT, R. M. ROBERTS and J. G. TILLET, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1982, 1569.
38. P. FUGEDI and P. J. GAREGG, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1986, **149**, C9.
39. H. KUYAMA, T. NUKADA, Y. NAKAHARA and T. OGAWA, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1993, **34**, 2171.
40. T. NAKAGAWA, K. UENO, M. KASHIWA and J. WATANABE, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1994, **35**, 1921.
41. R. R. SCHMIDT, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1986, **25**, 212.